

UNITED4 Surveillance pilot report - Malta

1. Describe the aim and objectives of your pilot study
Please attach the pilot plan drafted prior to start and/or provide the U4S TEAMS link to this document.

In Malta we had two parallel projects running in relation to WP3

Project A (GI Surveillance): Protocol for Implementing an Infectious Gastrointestinal Surveillance System in Malta

The main aim of the project is to **establish a comprehensive, automated surveillance system for infectious GI illnesses in the Maltese islands and assess the burden of GI disease and their impact on hospitalisations.**

Project B (MIDISS): Proposal for the establishment of the Malta Infectious Disease Integrated Surveillance System (MIDISS)

The project focused on developing a proposal for the EU4Health Direct Grant on improving and strengthening national surveillance systems with the main aim of establishing a harmonised and secure interoperable surveillance system that generates a real-time digital data stream that provides the information needed to timely and effectively fight cross-border threats to public health from infectious diseases.

2. Describe the expected output prior to start of the pilot

GI Surveillance: The project initially intended to focus on developing a protocol to establish a syndromic surveillance system for gastrointestinal illnesses by piloting the new IT platform in state hospitals (Patient Dashboard Platform) which would allow for systematic inputting of data. Due to unforeseen circumstances the launch of the system was delayed indefinitely and therefore the protocol focused on developing regular automated surveillance outputs using the currently available laboratory and hospital data.

MIDISS: The expected output was the development of a comprehensive proposal to improving and strengthening the national surveillance system by establishing a Public Health IT infrastructure that would allow for real-time automated surveillance using data from various stakeholders.

3. Briefly describe the method(s) used

GI Surveillance: Mapping of data from the state hospital and centralised laboratory system was conducted to identify the relevant data sources and variables needed. Using unique identifiers data from various sources was linked using R coding and weekly surveillance reports issued to assist in monitoring trends and disease burden.

MIDISS: Regular internal meetings were held within the Directorate and with relevant technical entities to identify the needs and requirements to establish such a platform. Several meetings were also held with stakeholders from which data would be utilised for surveillance, these include the Primary Health Care, State hospitals, Blood Bank and the veterinary sectors amongst others.

4. Report the principal finding(s) of your pilot study

GI Surveillance: Weekly internal GI surveillance reports issued to support in monitoring and outbreak detection. Findings highlight that GI pathogens are still a public health concern with potential considerable burden on the health system.

MIDISS: Not applicable. The proposal was accepted, and the actual project started on 1st January 2025.

5. Formulate your main take-away(s) and recommendations of your pilot study and provide rationale(s)

GI Surveillance: The project highlighted data quality issues and the importance of having adequate surveillance standards and IT infrastructures to allow for standardisation and analysis of data.

MIDISS: The project highlighted the importance of having integrated and secure IT infrastructures in health to allow for real-time automated surveillance to enhance public health preparedness and response.

6. Reflect on most relevant limitations and/or challenges (including potential solutions) and the degree of achieving expected output of your pilot study

GI Surveillance: Several challenges and limitations were encountered that would not allow for syndromic surveillance. The main challenges include lack of appropriate and timely ICD-10 coding at hospital level; paediatric data still predominantly paper-based; electronic data being inputted in free text format. These issues do not allow for standardisation of data and subsequent analysis and automation. The future implementation of the Patient Dashboard system in state hospitals would assist in improving data quality and access and hence in having a more robust surveillance system for syndromic surveillance. Further challenges and recommendations as highlighted in the project document.

MIDISS: Through the implementation of MIDISS Malta aims to close several gaps with regards to public health surveillance. Main challenges include the multitude of data sources from different stakeholders that will feed into MIDISS. These sources all have different data infrastructures which are constantly being updated and that have their own data quality issues. The proposal was successfully accepted, and the project is expected to be completed by 2028.

7. Did your pilot study contribute to strengthened (inter)national infectious disease surveillance? Why or why not?

GI Surveillance: The project served to establish automated weekly surveillance reports for GI pathogens thus assisting in routine monitoring and outbreak detection primarily at national level. The weekly reports also monitor the disease burden from GI pathogens thus supporting timely public health response and guiding policy.

MIDISS will include the acquisition of a cutting-edge Public Health Surveillance IT infrastructure equipped with automated and secure data loading from various sources, storage in a secure data warehouse, automated data transformation scripts, alongside an intuitive user dashboard for the creation of routine and configurable ad-hoc surveillance outputs. The projects scope aligns with Malta's IT obligations as an EU Member State to bear the responsibility of diligently monitoring and promptly reporting health concerns to the ECDC and other international partners.

UNITED4 Surveillance legal/privacy barriers (template)

1. To what degree did you experience legal/privacy barrier(s) in your pilot study?

No Little Some Large Very large

Malta has a robust legal infrastructure that allows for public health surveillance. The following laws help support surveillance activities.

The **Health Act** defines the role of the Department of Health Regulation including "to prevent communicable and non-communicable diseases and carry out surveillance and control in order to protect the general public from such diseases" <https://legislation.mt/eli/ln/2013/391/eng>

Mandatory reporting of notifiable diseases: The **Public Health Act** of Malta obliges clinicians and laboratories to report notifiable infectious disease to public health authority as part of the prevention and control of infectious diseases CAP. 465 Part IV <https://legislation.mt/eli/cap/465/eng/pdf>

Subsidiary Legislation 528.10 on **Processing of Personal Data (Secondary Processing - Health Sector)**, allows the processing of personal data for the purpose of public health surveillance. <https://legislation.mt/eli/sl/528.10/eng>

In addition to the legislation the Health Promotion and Disease Prevention Directorate has official data sharing agreements with main stakeholders such as the Primary Health Care and Mater Dei Hospital.

2. If so, please provide a detailed example(s) on the experienced legal/privacy barrier(s) in your pilot study.

N/A

3. How did you cope with and/or solve the experienced legal and/or privacy barrier within your pilot study? If not, what is your suggestion to solve this legal/privacy barrier(s) in the future?

N/A